

Life cycle based environmental impacts of energy
system transformation strategies for Germany:
Additional results from the InNOSys project

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1 Introduction

This report documents additional results from the study [4]. For each of the seventeen environmental indicators summarized in Table 1, the following results are shown in Section 2:

- Development of the indicator 2000-2050 on scenario level
- Environmental impacts for the year 2050 on the level of those sectors explicitly considered in the foreground model. A list of model sectors can be found below in Section 4.1.
- Environmental impacts for the year 2050 on the level of end-use applications. An overview of end-use applications considered here can be found in Section 4.2.
- Environmental impacts for the year 2050 on the level of individual technologies (impacts from construction and operation separated). In the figures, only technologies contributing more than 5% to the total impact on scenario level are shown individually. The impacts of all other technologies are shown in an aggregated manner.
- Environmental impacts for the year 2050, separated into direct impacts (from on-site emissions during operation of the technologies) and impacts from background processes (impacts from the construction of the technologies, impacts from the generation of fuels not explicitly considered in the foreground model, ...).
- Cumulated impacts (2020-2050) on the level of sectors explicitly considered in the foreground model (see Section 4.1).

In Section 3, the performance of all scenarios with respect to all indicators is compared, both on the level of entire scenarios, but also on the level of individual sectors (residential, service, industry, transport, power generation, P2X and biofuel conversion).

Note that the scenarios I-V achieve a reduction of (direct) CO₂ emissions of ca. 80%. They are thus called the "80% scenarios". Scenarios VI-X achieve a reduction of (direct) CO₂ emissions of ca. 95% and are called the "95% scenarios".

A detailed description of the methods applied here as well as a principal discussion of the approach can be found in [2] and [3].

Category	Indicator	unit
Climate Change	Climate change	kg CO ₂ eq
Ecosystem Quality	Freshwater and terrestrial acidification	mol H ⁺ eq
	Freshwater ecotoxicity	CTUe
	Freshwater eutrophication	kg P eq
	Marine eutrophication	kg N eq
	Terrestrial eutrophication	mo N eq
Human Health	Carcinogenic effects	CTUh
	Non-carcinogenic effects	CTUh
	Ionizing radiation	kg U235 eq
	Ozone layer depletion	kg CFC-11 eq
	Photochemical ozone creation	kg NMVOC eq
	Respiratory effects, inorganics	disease incidence
Resources	Fossils	MJ
	Minerals and metals	kg Sb eq
	Land use	points
	Dissipated water	m ³ water eq
EU Environmental footprint	EU Environmental footprint	dimensionless

Table 1: Overview of life cycle based environmental impacts assessed here. All indicators are calculated with the methods summarized in [1], with the exception of Resources (minerals and metals), which uses the method from [5].

2 Additional results for individual indicators

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PowerAndDHGeneration not cumulated average

Figure 105: Comparison of normalized results for 2050 for *power and district heat generation* (power plants, heating plants, CHP plants). Red line: Average normalized indicator values for all 80% scenarios in 2050. Red area: Range of normalized results for all 80% indicators in 2050. Blue line and blue area: same for 95% scenarios. Green dashed line: Results for base year. All results are normalized to the average of all scenarios in 2050.

Transport not cumulated average

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Residential not cumulated average

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Residential not cumulated average

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Residential not cumulated average

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Residential not cumulated average

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4 Additional Information

4.1 Model sectors

The following sectors are explicitly modeled in the foreground systems:

- Residential Sector
 - Generation of space heat (SH)
 - Generation of hot water (HW)
 - CHP autoproduction (generation of space heat, hot water, and electricity)
- Industry Sector
 - Generation of space heat and hot water (SH/HW)
 - Generation of process heat (PH)
 - CHP autoproduction (generation of process heat, space heat, hot water, and electricity)
- Sector Services (incl. Trade and Commerce)
 - Generation of space heat and hot water (SH/HW)
 - Generation of process heat (PH)
 - CHP autoproduction (generation of process heat, space heat, hot water, and electricity)
- Transport
 - Road passenger transport
 - Road freight transport
 - Rail transport (passengers and freight)
 - Aviation (passenger and freight)
 - Navigation
- Conversion Sector (national)
 - Power Plants (w/o public CHP plans)
 - Power Storage
 - (Public) CHP Plants
 - Heating Plants
 - Generation of synthetic fuels and gases
 - Bioenergy conversion
- Other sectors
 - Imports of (renewable) power
 - Imports of (renewable) synthetic fuels and gases
 - Non-energy demand

4.2 End-use Applications

Environmental impacts on the level of model sectors are allocated to the following end-use applications:

- Residential Sector
 - Generation of space heat (including Power-to-Space-Heat)
 - Generation of hot water (including Power-to-Hot-Water)
 - Electric Appliances (w/o electric appliances for the generation of space heat and hot water)
- Industry Sector
 - Generation of space heat and hot water (including Power-to-Space-Heat-And-Hot-Water)
 - Generation of process heat (including Power-to-Process-Heat)
 - Electric Appliances (w/o electric appliances for the generation of process heat, space heat and hot water)
- Services Sector (including trade and commerce)
 - Generation of space heat and hot water (including Power-to-Space-Heat-And-Hot-Water)
 - Generation of process heat (including Power-to-Process-Heat)
 - Electric Appliances (w/o electric appliances for the generation of process heat, space heat and hot water)
- Transport
 - Road passenger transport
 - Road freight transport
 - Rail passenger transport
 - Rail freight transport
 - Aviation (passenger)
 - Aviation (freight)
 - Navigation
- Others
 - Non-energy demand

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Note

The quantitative impact assessment results are also published in an Excel file on the project home page, see <https://www.innosys-projekt.de/en>.